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PATHOGENETIC JUSTIFICATION OF CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH PEPTIC ULCER OF THE STOMACH AND DUODENUM COMBINED WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

Резюме.

У статті висвітлено патогенетичні зміни та їх обґрунтування у хворих на пептичну виразку шлунка та дванадцятипалої кишки у поєднанні з цукровим діабетом типу 2. Встановлені зміни з боку ліпідного профілю, глюкози в крові, глікозильованого гемоглобіну.

Summary.

The article highlights pathogenetic changes and their justification in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus. Changes in the lipid profile, blood glucose, and glycosylated hemoglobin were identified.

Keywords. ulcer, stomach, duodenal ulcer, diabetes mellitus, sugar, glycosylated hemoglobin.

Ключові слова: виразка, шлунок, дванадцятипала кишка, цукровий діабет, цукор, глікозильований гемоглобін.

Introduction. Peptic ulcer disease remains one of the current problems in the field of gastroenterology today. One of the key factors contributing to its development is infection with the bacterium *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*, HP). In particular, the presence of certain toxigenic strains of this bacterium (*cagA*, *vacA*, *babA*, *iceA*) is associated with a more severe course of the pathology and an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases. This fact became the basis for a detailed study of the influence of *H. pylori* infection and its strains on the development of diseases such as arterial hypertension, atherosclerosis and type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Helicobacter pylori* is able to change the processes of insulin secretion, which leads to an increase in insulin resistance, which is one of the factors in the progression of type 2 diabetes mellitus. The combination of these pathological conditions creates particularly unfavorable conditions for the patient [1,2].

It is known that chronic inflammation is a key pathogenetic mechanism in the formation of type 2 diabetes mellitus. This results in prolonged, low-grade inflammation that gradually disrupts the body's metabolic balance. *H. pylori* infection may serve as an additional stimulus for activating a systemic inflammatory response [3].

Materials and methods of the study. To verify the diagnosis of PG of the stomach and duodenum, esophagogastroduodenoscopy with targeted biopsy was performed using the "GIFQ-40" device from the Olympus company (Japan) according to the generally

accepted methodology. The characteristics of endoscopic changes in the mucous membrane of the stomach and duodenum were carried out using the minimum standard terminology. Inflammatory and atrophic changes in the CO were assessed by degrees: 0 - absence of signs, 1 - minimal degree, 2 - moderate and 3 - pronounced. Diagnosis of NR was carried out using a rapid urease test with biopsy material, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with a biopsy and urease breath test using the "Helik" test system with indicator tubes ("AMA"). The level of glycemia was examined by the glucose oxidase method using standard sets of reagents produced by NPP "Filisit diagnostics" (Ukraine). Glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) was determined by a photolorimetric method using a set of reagents from the company "SpineLab" (Kharkiv, Ukraine).

Results of the study. Laboratory examination of patients with combined pathology - peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum together with type 2 diabetes mellitus - showed that the level of erythrocytes fluctuates in the upper limit of the norm, while the hemoglobin concentration is kept at the lower limit of the norm. The number of leukocytes in patients with combined pathology was also close to the upper limit of the norm. An increase in the erythrocyte sedimentation rate was observed in all studied groups. As for hematocrit, it decreased in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, while in patients with this ulcer on the background of type 2 diabetes mellitus, its increase was recorded (see Table 1).

Evaluation of complete blood count in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum in combination with type 2 diabetes mellitus, %.

Indicators /groups	Erythrocytes, G/l	Hemoglobin, G/l	Color index	Leukocytes G/l	ESR, Mm/h	Glucose (μmol/L)	Hematocrit, %
PG (n= 13)	4,3±0,16 p ₂ <0,05	122±3,23	0,9±0,09	3,6±0,16 p ₂ <0,05 p ₃ <0,05	26±1,2	5,9±0,2 p ₂ <0,05	32±1,94 p ₂ <0,05 p ₃ <0,05
PD (n= 7)	4,0±0,12	131±4,08	0,9±0,09	4,2±0,24 p ₂ <0,05 p ₃ <0,05	24±1,19	5,8±0,17	34±1,95 p ₂ <0,05 p ₃ <0,05
PG and DM2 (n= 12)	5,6±0,2	128±3,5	0,9±0,09	9,6±0,86	24±1,19	7,6±0,29	49±2,15
PD and DM2 (n= 8)	5,2±0,18	127±3,46	0,76±0,06	9,2±0,81	20±1,14	6,8±0,26	48±2,15

Notes. p – significance of differences in indicators relative to a group of practically healthy individuals; p₁ – significance of differences in indicators relative to the group on PD; p₂ – significance of differences in indicators relative to the group on PD with DM2; p₃ – significance of differences in indicators relative to the group on PD with DM2.

When assessing the lipid profile in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum on the background of type 2 diabetes mellitus, a significant increase in total cholesterol was found compared to a group of practically healthy individuals by 2.01% and 1.72%, respectively. At the same time, no significant changes in the level of total cholesterol were observed

in patients without comorbidities. High-density lipoproteins (HDL) were significantly reduced in all groups, while the level of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) was increased. The atherogenic index (AI) in the studied groups was 4.94; 3.82; 6.51 and 5.31, which indicates a severe course of the disease, especially in the presence of comorbidities (Table 2).

Table.2**Blood lipid spectrum in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum in combination with type 2 diabetes mellitus, M±m.**

Indicators	Groups				Healthy individuals n =20
	PG and PD		PG and PD with DM2		
	PG n =13	PD n =7	PG with DM2 n =12	PD with DM2 n =8	
Total cholesterol, (mmol/l)	5,2±0,29	4,1±0,26	6,8±0,21 */#	6,9±0,21 */#	4,08±0,07
HDL, (mmol/l)	0,89±0,07 *	0,99±0,06 *	0,81±0,06 *	0,87±0,07 *	1,42±0,15
LDL, (mmol/l)	2,91±0,3 *	2,94±0,13 *	3,62±0,16 */#	3,57±0,15 */#	2,19±0,39
IA	4,94±0,49 *	3,82±0,56 *	6,51±0,73 */#	5,31±0,26 */#	2,63±0,52

Notes. * - significant differences (p<0.05) between the indicators in the groups of PVS and DU combined with DM2 in comparison with the PZO group; # - significant differences (p<0.05) between the indicators in the PVS and DU groups with the groups of patients with PVS and DU with DM2

When analyzing the impact of *Helicobacter pylori* infection in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum on the background of type 2 diabetes

mellitus, it was found that these groups had increased levels of blood glucose and glycosylated hemoglobin (Table 3).

Table.3

Levels of glycosylated hemoglobin and blood glucose in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus, $M \pm m$.

Indicators/groups	Glucose ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	HbA1c, %
PG (n= 13)	5,9 \pm 0,2 [#] $p_2 < 0,05$	6,0 \pm 0,18 [#] $p_2 < 0,05$
PD (n= 7)	5,8 \pm 0,17	5,8 \pm 0,17
PG and DM2 (n= 12)	7,6 \pm 0,29	7,1 \pm 0,21
PD and DM2 (n= 8)	6,8 \pm 0,26	6,8 \pm 0,20

Notes. * - significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the indicators in the groups of PVS and DU combined with DM2 in comparison with the PZO group;
- significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the indicators in the PVS and DU groups with the groups of patients with PVS and DU with DM2

Justification of results. During laboratory examination of patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum in combination with type 2 diabetes mellitus, it was found that the level of erythrocytes fluctuates at the upper limit of normal, the level of hemoglobin — at the lower limit, and leukocytes — also at the upper limit of normal in patients with combined pathology. The erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) was increased in all groups. Hematocrit was found to be reduced in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, while in patients with the same pathology on the background of DM2 it had a tendency to increase. An increased number of leukocytes, even if it remained within normal limits, is associated with chronic complications that develop in type 2 diabetes mellitus. In combination with other markers, chronic inflammation may play an important role in the pathogenesis and progression of complications associated with diabetes [6,8]. Although there are generally accepted risk factors that influence the development of these complications, they do not fully explain the entire excess risk. Recent studies have increasingly focused on inflammatory factors, in particular the role of leukocytes in the progression of diabetic complications [2,7]. In patients with peptic ulcer and duodenal ulcer against the background of toxigenic strains of *H. pylori*, changes in the cytokine profile are observed - an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6, IL-12, IL-18) and a decrease in anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10). Leukocytes can be activated by glycation end products, oxidative stress and angiotensin II, which are formed as a result of hyperglycemia, producing factors such as tumor necrosis factor- α and interleukin β 1, which are involved in the development of chronic complications of diabetes [3,5]. Higher leukocyte counts correlate with both macrovascular and microvascular complications [8]. Chronic inflammation is considered one of the key mechanisms of the onset and progression of type 2 diabetes, which indicates the importance of immunological and inflammatory processes in the pathogenesis of the disease [9]. There is also a hypothesis that low insulin levels stimulate the formation of neutrophils in the bone marrow [10]. At the same time, receptors have been found in the immune system of diabetic patients that initiate inflammatory reactions in the vessels, which, along with other risk factors, enhances the progression of complications, causing significant damage to the endothelium and an increase in the level of inflammatory mediators and oxidative stress [9,11]. The concentration of hemoglobin is closely related to

the course of diabetes, as patients with this disease are more vulnerable to anemia and its consequences [2, 3]. Hematocrit is positively correlated with hyperinsulinemia and associated conditions of insulin resistance, including elevated blood pressure, elevated triglycerides, low HDL, and central obesity, supporting its association with insulin resistance. In addition, hematocrit is an important determinant of blood viscosity [4, 5, 9]. Peptic ulcer disease of the stomach and duodenum in the setting of type 2 diabetes is associated with a tendency toward hypercoagulability, which is manifested by an increase in the level of fibrinogen, antithrombin III activity, a decrease in the activity of chromium-dependent factor, as well as an increase in total, enzymatic and non-enzymatic fibrinolytic activity. At the same time, the level of coagulation factor XIII decreases [7]. The morphofunctional properties of erythrocytes are disrupted, which leads to the development of hypercoagulability syndrome, which is characterized by a reduction in blood clotting time against the background of a decrease in total fibrinolytic activity (in particular, enzymatic) and an increase in non-enzymatic fibrinolytic activity due to the presence of underoxidized products characteristic of diabetes mellitus. The activity of antithrombin III and factor XIII also decreases, the internal mechanism of fibrinolysis is depleted, and the potential of plasminogen decreases. One of the causes of hypercoagulable disorders in this combined pathology is considered to be the deterioration of the morphofunctional properties of erythrocytes, and increased non-enzymatic fibrinolysis is considered as one of the mechanisms of compensation for these changes [9,10,12].

Elevated total cholesterol levels in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus are due to the development of insulin resistance, which negatively affects lipid metabolism in the body. In particular, insulin resistance stimulates increased synthesis of very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) in the liver and also causes a decrease in lipoprotein lipase activity, which leads to the accumulation of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) and total cholesterol in the blood [1,4]. Increased blood glucose levels are accompanied by an increase in lipid concentrations, which can lead to increased oxidative stress, inflammatory reactions and endothelial dysfunction, worsening the course of gastric and duodenal ulcers [4,5]. Inadequate glycemic control also increases the likelihood of developing microvascular complications, such as nephropathy, neuropathy and retinopathy, which often accompany diabetes [4,6]. Hyperglycemia

disrupts lipid metabolism through various pathways: it activates lipolysis, stimulates triglyceride synthesis, and reduces lipoprotein lipase activity. In addition, insulin resistance in patients with type 2 diabetes contributes to dyslipidemia by increasing hepatic VLDL production and decreasing LDL clearance from the bloodstream [2,3,8,12].

Conclusion. The study revealed lipid profile abnormalities (total cholesterol — TCA ($p < 0.05$), LDL ($p < 0.05$), HDL ($p < 0.05$), atherogenic index — IA ($p < 0.05$)) in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum in combination with type 2 diabetes mellitus. At the same time, a slight increase in blood glucose levels was observed ($p < 0.05$) in patients without concomitant pathology, as well as an increase in glycosylated hemoglobin ($p < 0.05$). Insulin resistance in these patients contributes to an increase in the production of very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) in the liver and a decrease in the activity of lipoprotein lipase, which leads to the accumulation of LDL and total cholesterol in the blood. The combination of peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, associated with *Helicobacter pylori*, and type 2 diabetes mellitus is accompanied by an increase in hematocrit levels ($p < 0.05$), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) ($p < 0.05$), and leukocytes ($p < 0.05$), which reflects a chronic inflammatory process and changes in the rheological properties of the blood.

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